

UTILIZING TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE STUDENTS’ COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE SKILLS

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Abstract: In today's digital age, technology plays a crucial role in improving students' communicative knowledge. With the widespread use of smartphones, tablets, laptops, and other digital devices, students have access to a wealth of resources that can help them develop their communication skills. One effective way to use technology to improve students' communicative knowledge is through online communication tools such as email, social media, and instant messaging. By using these tools, students can practice their writing skills, learn how to communicate effectively in a digital environment, and develop their ability to express themselves clearly and concisely. In this article the strategies and concepts are presented to improve students' communicative skills using technology

Key words: technology, technology-based teaching, communicative skills, knowledge.

Introduction

To use technology to improve students' communicative knowledge is through video conferencing and online collaboration tools is also considered a good way of improving communicative skills. These tools allow students to work together on projects, share ideas, and communicate with each other in real-time, regardless of their physical location. By using these tools, students can learn how to collaborate effectively with others, develop their teamwork skills, and improve their ability to communicate complex ideas. Furthermore, technology can also be used to improve students' listening skills. With the availability of podcasts, online videos, and audio recordings, students can listen to a variety of sources and practice their comprehension skills. Teachers can also use online quizzes and assessments to test students' listening skills and provide feedback on areas that need improvement.

Using technology to boost students receptive skills

In today's fast-paced digital world, technology has become an integral part of our daily lives. From smartphones to laptops and tablets, technology has revolutionized the way we communicate, learn, and interact with each other. In the education sector, technology has played a significant role in enhancing students' learning experience and improving their receptive skills.

Receptive skills refer to the ability to understand and comprehend information through listening and reading. These skills are essential for effective communication and critical thinking. Using technology to boost students' receptive skills can help them become better listeners, readers, and learners. Here are some ways technology can be used to improve students' receptive skills:

1. Online Reading and Listening Resources

The internet is a vast resource of reading and listening materials that can help students improve their receptive skills. Teachers can use online platforms such as podcasts, audiobooks, and news articles to provide students with engaging and informative content. These resources can be tailored to the students' level and interests, making learning more enjoyable and effective.

2. Interactive Learning Platforms

Interactive learning platforms such as Kahoot, Quizlet, and Duolingo can help students improve their receptive skills through gamification. These platforms use quizzes, games, and interactive activities to engage students and reinforce their learning. Teachers can use these platforms to test students' comprehension and provide immediate feedback.

3. Language Learning Apps

Language learning apps such as Babbel, Rosetta Stone, and Memrise can help students improve their receptive skills in a foreign language. These apps use interactive activities, games, and quizzes to teach vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. Students can practice listening and reading comprehension through audio recordings and written texts.

4. Speech Recognition Software

Speech recognition software such as Dragon Naturally Speaking can help students improve their listening skills by transcribing spoken words into text. Students can listen to audio recordings or watch videos and then use the software to transcribe what they hear. This can help them become better listeners and develop their transcription skills.

5. Virtual Reality

Virtual reality technology can provide students with immersive learning experiences that can improve their receptive skills. For example, students can use VR headsets to explore historical sites, museums, and natural environments. This can help them develop their listening and reading comprehension skills by providing them with a visual and auditory context. Technology can be a powerful tool for improving students' receptive skills. By incorporating technology into their lessons, teachers can create an engaging and interactive learning environment that fosters effective communication skills and prepares their students for success in both personal and professional settings.

Using technology to improve productive skills

In addition to improving students' receptive skills, technology can also be used to boost their productive skills, specifically speaking and writing. These skills are essential for effective communication and critical thinking, and technology can provide students with the tools and resources they need to develop them.

Here are some ways technology can be used to improve students' productive skills:

1. Online Writing Tools

The internet is a vast resource of writing tools that can help students improve their writing skills. Teachers can use online platforms such as Grammarly, Hemingway Editor, and ProWritingAid to provide students with real-time feedback on their writing. These tools can help students identify grammar and spelling errors, improve their sentence structure, and enhance the readability of their writing.

2. Collaborative Writing Platforms

Collaborative writing platforms such as Google Docs and Microsoft Word can help students develop their writing skills by allowing them to work together on a single document. This can help students learn how to collaborate effectively, provide feedback to their peers, and develop their writing skills through peer review.

3. Voice Recording Apps

Voice recording apps such as Voice Memo and Audacity can help students improve their speaking skills by allowing them to record and listen to their own voice. This can help students identify areas where they need improvement, such as pronunciation or intonation, and work on developing these skills.

4. Video Conferencing

Video conferencing platforms such as Zoom and Skype can help students improve their speaking skills by allowing them to communicate with others in real-time. This can help students develop their conversational skills, practice speaking in a group setting, and learn how to communicate effectively using digital tools.

5. Language Learning Apps

Language learning apps such as Duolingo and Memrise can help students improve their speaking skills in a foreign language. These apps use interactive activities, games, and quizzes to teach vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. Students can practice speaking through audio recordings and speaking exercises.

References:

1. Wiseman, R. L. (2002). Intercultural communication competence. In W. B. Gudykunst, & B. Mody (Eds.), Handbook of international and intercultural communication(2nd ed), (pp. 207-224). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
2. Алимжорова, М. (2022). ТАЪЛИМНИНГ ГЛОБАЛЛАШУВИ ШАРОИТИДА ТАЛАБАЛАРДА МАДАНИЯТЛАРАРО МУЛОҚОТ

КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ЗАРУРАТИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(B3), 254-263.

3. Mirzaev, A. B. U. (2022). IMPROVING EFL/ESL CLASSROOMS THROUGH USING ONLINE PLATFORMS: NEARPOD–AS AN EXAMPLE OF TOP-RATED ONLINE EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 264-270.

4. Gafurova, N. I. (2021). Structural-semantic classification of construction terms in English and Uzbek languages. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(5), 571-575.

5. Hoshimova, N. A. (2020). Ingliz va o'zbek tillarining funktsional uslublari. *Молодой ученый*, (19), 584-585.

6. Mirzayev, A., & Oripova, S. (2022). COMMUNICATIVE METHOD–A NEW APPROACH IN THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 778-783.

7. Алимжонова, М. (2022). ГЛОБАЛЛАШУВНИНГ МАДАНИЯТЛАРАРО МУЛОҚОТГА ТАЪСИРИ ВА УНИ ТАДҚИҚ ЭТИШНИНГ ИЛМИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК АСОСЛАРИ. *INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 3(3), 323-328.

8. Абдухалимова, С. (2022). THE CONCEPT AND CONTENT OF INTERCULTURAL DISCOURSE. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(4).

9. Abdumutaljonovna, P. S. (2022). The function and peculiarities of advertising text in linguistics. *Confrencea*, 1(1).

10. Kosimova, M. U. (2021). Different classification of functional styles. *Ученый XX века*. 4 (85).7-8.

11. Bahridinov, M. M., Turgunov, D. B., & Tojiboyev, I. M. (2020). SOME PROBLEMS OF LEXICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE NOVEL ULYSSES BY JAMES JOYCE. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(1), 208-212.

12. Ahundjanova, M. A. (2020). METHODS AND METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE. *Экономика и социум*, (11), 46-49.